

*Devyāmata*, chapter 78: the names of the vāstu deities, translation.

78.1 The deities, Brahmā, etc., are known by particular names. In the centre of the vāstu, four-faced Brahmā is Jagatpati.

78.2 Hara is Lokeśvara himself. Parjanya is Meghanāthaka. Jayanta is Kāśyapa. Mahendra is Sureśvara.

78.3 Āditya is Bhāskara. Satya is Dharma. Bhṛṣa is Kāmadeva. Antarīkṣa is Ambara.

78.4 Agni is Hutāśana. Pūṣan is the Mātṛgaṇa. Yama is himself. Gandharva is Nārada.

78.5 Bhṛṅga is Nirṛti. Mṛgo is Adharma. The Piṭṛs are the Piṭṛdevas, dwelling in Piṭṛloka.

78.6 Dvauvārika is Nandi. Sugrīva is Manu. Puṣpadanta is Garutmant. Varuṇa is Apāmpati.

78.7 Asura is Rāhu. Śoṣa is the moving planet Saturn (Śani). Pāpayakṣman is Kṣaya. Roga is Vāyu.

78.4 Vitatha and Gṛhakṣata would be expected between Pūṣan and Yama.

78.8 Nāga is Vāsuki. Mukhya is Viśvakarman. Bhalvāṭa is Candramā. Soma is Kubera.

78.9 Ananta is Caraka. Aditi is Śrī. Diti is Śarva, with trident in hand and a bull pennant.

78.10 Āpa is the Himavant mountain. Āpavatsa is Umā. Aryaman is Āditya. Sāvitrī is Vedamātrka.

78.11 Savitṛ is Gaṅgā. Vivasvant is ? Indra is Harijaya. Indrajaya is Vajra.

78.12 Mitra is Halāyudha. Rudra is Maheśvara. Rājayaḥṣman is Guha. Pṛthivīdhara is Meru.

78.13 Forty five deities are taught in the vāstu body. And four other attendants to the deities are outside the vāstu.

78.14 They are stationed at the corners, from the northeast onwards, as Carakī [etc.]. The position of the deities in the vāstu body has been given.

78.15 Next hear about the classification of sirās, and so forth, and vulnerable points (marmans).

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78.11b ‡ ‡ akaḥ: I cannot come up with a sensible proposition here.

78.14b carakyā: The instrumental is an oddity, but agreed upon by all the manuscripts.

78.15a sirādi: The sirās are among a set of lines that cross the site. Their positions are important to the determination of the vulnerable points (marmans) of the site. See sections 2.6 and 2.7 of the general introduction. They will be described in the next chapter.